

THE HARMFUL PEST OF THE TOMATO PLANT, LIRIOMYZA BRYONIAE, AND STRATEGIES FOR MITIGATING ITS ECONOMIC DAMAGE

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Abstract. In our conducted studies, a suspension of the insecticide TUTARIPS 35% EC was applied against the pest *Liriomyza bryoniae*, which inflicts significant damage to tomato plants grown in enclosed environments by feeding on the epidermal tissue of the leaves. This results in the disruption of photosynthesis and metabolic processes, ultimately reducing yield. The insecticide demonstrated high efficacy, with its insecticidal activity reaching 88.5–91.0% by the 7th day.

Keywords: family Agromyzidae, species, *Liriomyza bryoniae*, fly, pest, preparation, biological effectiveness.

Introduction: Improving food security for the population and enhancing the efficiency of agricultural production are largely dependent on the modernization of agricultural sectors. The scientifically established annual consumption standards for vegetables require that they be consumed uniformly throughout the year. To achieve this, it is essential to develop open and protected land vegetable cultivation in a balanced manner. In ensuring that the population is supplied with vegetable products during the late autumn, winter, and early spring months, protected land vegetable cultivation plays a critically important role [6].

The abundant sunshine in our republic provides extensive opportunities for the development of irrigated agriculture. On the other hand, these climatic conditions also favor the proliferation of various pests that damage agricultural crops. Under the conditions of Central Asia, almost all pest species develop rapidly and can produce several generations in a year compared to the northern regions. This necessitates a profound understanding of the biology of pests, their interrelationship with plants and the environment, and the implementation of the most effective pest control measures and tools for plant protection [12].

In greenhouses, pests such as the tomato borer and the cucumber moth cause serious damage to crops like tomatoes and cucumbers. Therefore, it becomes an urgent task to identify the most effective pesticides against pests like the tomato moth in greenhouse cultivation and to recommend their production for use [7].

For this reason, it is required to study in depth the biological development characteristics of these pests and the damage they cause, and to scientifically justify integrated pest control measures. This should involve the creation of a set of economically efficient and environmentally friendly methods and tools that minimize ecological disruption [2].

In our republic, preserving crop yield by perfecting the pest protection system in tomato cultivation is of utmost importance. In tomato production, pests and diseases can cause yield losses ranging from 10% to 90% of the total crop. Consequently, ensuring food safety in our country and

securing a recognized position in the global market significantly depend on the production of products using scientifically based technologies and tools [4].

The most dangerous pest of the tomato is the tomato moth, which primarily feeds on the stems, fruits, growth points, axils, and floral clusters of the tomato plant. If the appropriate control measures are not implemented in a timely manner, pest damage can affect 50–60% or even more of the tomato yield.

Tomato leafminer (*Tuta absoluta*) also feeds on other solanaceous crops such as potato, tobacco, eggplant, and pepper, as well as on various wild plants including *Datura*, *Physalis*, wild nightshade (*Solanum nigrum*), and others. It affects tomato plants throughout their entire growing season, both in greenhouses and open fields. The larval (caterpillar) stage is responsible for causing the damage [3].

When food is abundant, the larvae do not enter diapause. They feed on leaf and stem tissues, creating large, irregularly shaped galleries and mines. These mines allow entry points for various microorganisms, particularly fungi, which lead to rot and mold in leaves and fruits. As a result, fruits may rot during development or storage [1].

Adult moths are nocturnal and hide among the foliage during the day. Female moths lay up to 300 eggs in a lifetime (with an average of 260). Typically, the larvae hatch 4–7 days after egg-laying. About 73% of the eggs are deposited on leaves, 21% on leaf veins and stems, 5% on sepals, and 1% on fruits. Newly hatched larvae are pale yellowish, about 0.5 mm in length, with a black head. In their 2nd to 4th instars, they become light brown or yellowish-green. They develop through four larval stages over a period of 4–15 days (on average 8-days). Mature larvae reach

8–9 mm in length and pupate by spinning a silk cocoon, often within the leaf mines. The pest can overwinter in egg, pupa, or adult stages.

The minimum temperature for development is 9°C, with the optimal range between 20–27°C. One generation completes in 30–35 days under normal conditions, 24 days in optimal temperatures, and up to 76 days at 14°C [8].

In recent years, global research has focused on several key strategies for managing tomato pests, including: studying the bioecology and developmental characteristics of adventive pest species; identifying the factors influencing their reproduction; expanding the use and application of environmentally safe microbial pesticides; assessing the biological efficacy of modern insecticides from different chemical groups; and improving integrated pest management (IPM) systems for widespread implementation in crop production [3].

To address these challenges, researchers have developed a chemical pesticide called TUTARIPS 35% EC for use against tomato pests. Based on trial results, it is believed that the broad application of this product in agricultural fields can play a significant role in overcoming the aforementioned issues.

Research Materials and Methods.

In 2024, trials were conducted in a greenhouse located in Kibray district of Tashkent region, at the “Boburxoja Nodirkhoja Baraka” LLC, to control one of the main pests of tomato—the tomato leaf miner moth (*Tuta absoluta*)—using the pesticide TUTARIPS 35% EC at application rates of 0.6–1.0 liter.

The timing of pest emergence and population counts were carried out in accordance with generally accepted methodologies developed by Osmolovskiy G.E. (1980) and Polyakov et al. (1984) [9,10].

Control measures against *Tuta absoluta* were initiated after flowering of the third tomato truss, when 23–27 larvae of the new generation were detected on the leaves of 10 sampled tomato plants. The experiment included treatment, reference, and control variants, with each variant replicated three times. Pest counts were performed before treatment and on days 3, 7, 14, and 21 after treatment. The efficacy of the pesticide was evaluated by comparing results with the untreated control variant. Field trials were conducted following the methodological guidelines by Khojaye Sh.T. (2023) [5]. Biological efficacy was calculated using the standard formula proposed by Püntener W. (1981) [11], as follows:

$$E = 1 - (Op \times Kd / Od \times Kp) \times 100$$

Where: **E** – Biological efficacy (%)

Od – Number of live pests before treatment in the treated variant

Op – Number of live pests after treatment in the treated variant

Kd – Number of live pests before treatment in the untreated control

Kp – Number of live pests after treatment in the untreated control.

Results and Discussion

Experimental trials of the chemical product TUTARIPS, 35% EC (active ingredients: *Etofenprox 250 g/L + Pyriproxyfen 100 g/L*), which acts against the tomato leafminer (*Tuta absoluta*), were conducted in September of the current year in greenhouse-grown tomatoes. The trials tested application rates of 0.6–1.0 liters per hectare. For comparison, KARMAIL PLUS EC, 10% EC (*Pyriproxyfen*) was used as the reference standard at a rate of 0.7 liters per hectare.

Table-1.

Biological effectiveness of the chemical preparation TUTARIPS, 35% e.c. against the tomato moth in greenhouses (Tashkent region, Kibray district "Boburkhoja Nodirhoja baraka" LLC variety: Pink paradayz F₁, 23.09.2024).

№	Experimental variants	Active ingredient	Preparation consumption rate.	Average number of moth larvae on 10 tomato plants, pcs.				Biological effectiveness %, days				
				Before spraying medicine	Number of days after injection				3	7	14	21
					3	7	14	21				
1.	TUTARIPS, 35% em.k.	<i>Etofenprox 250 g/l+ pyriproxyfen 100 g/l.</i>	0,6	24,4	6,4	3,0	4,2	10,3	73,7	88,5	85,7	73,0
			1,0	25,1	6,1	2,4	4,0	9,4	76,1	91,0	86,7	75,9
2.	KARMAIL PLUS EC, em.k. (sample).	<i>Pyriproxyfen</i>	0,7	23,6	6,6	3,4	5,1	11,2	72,5	86,5	82,1	69,5
3.	Control (unprocessed)	-	-	23,2	23,6	24,8	28,0	36,2	-	-	-	-

The effectiveness of TUTARIPS, 35% EC against the tomato leafminer was evaluated over a 21-day period following application. The trial results for the 0.6 liter application rate are presented in the table-1. As shown, before treatment, the average number of larvae per 10 tomato plants was 24.4. After application, larval numbers progressively decreased: 6.4 on day-3, 3.0 on day-7, 4.2 on day-14, and 10.3 on day-21. The corresponding biological efficacy was 73.7% on day-3, 88.5% on day-7, 85.7% on day-14, and 73.0% on day-21.

For the 1.0 liter application rate, the average larval count prior to spraying was 25.1. Post-treatment counts dropped to 6.1 on day-3, 2.4 on day-7, 4.0 on day-14, and 9.4 on day-21. Biological efficacy was calculated as 76.1% on day-3, 91.0% on day-7, 86.7% on day-14, and 75.9% on day-21. In the untreated control group, the initial average number of larvae was 23.2 per 10 plants. This number increased over time to 23.6 on day-3, 24.8 on day-7, 28.0 on day-14,

and 36.2 on day-21. In the reference variant treated with KARMAIL PLUS EC, 10% EC at 0.7 liter, the average number of larvae after treatment was 6.6 on day-3, 3.4 on day-7, 5.1 on day-14, and 11.2 on day-21. Biological efficacy for this treatment was 72.5%, 86.5%, 82.1%, and 69.5%, respectively. The highest efficacy for both the test and reference treatments was observed on day-7. However, a decline in insecticidal activity was noted in subsequent days.

Conclusion and Recommendations

When applied at rates of 0.6–1.0 liters per hectare, TUTARIPS, 35% EC demonstrated high biological efficacy (88.5–91.0%) against *Tuta absoluta* by the 7th day after application in greenhouse-grown tomatoes. The formulation is convenient to use and readily forms a working solution when mixed with water. No phytotoxic effects were observed on the plants. It is recommended to apply this product only when pest population levels reach the economic threshold, with careful attention to dosage rates to ensure effective and economically justified pest control.

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